

Review

Environmental enrichment in ruminants and equines: Introduction

Raphaëlle Botreau, Clémence Lesimple, Valentin Brunet, Isabelle Veissier

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Alice Ruet, Giuseppe de Rosa, Francesco Cerasoli, Luigi Iannetti, Michele podaliri Vulpiani and Emanuela Rossi for their contribution and Alison Hanlon and Cécile Ginane for reviewing the document.

Review

Environmental enrichment in ruminants and equines: Introduction

Raphaëlle Botreau¹, Clémence Lesimple¹, Valentin Brunet¹, Isabelle Veissier¹

¹Unité Mixte de Recherche sur les Herbivores, INRAE – Centre Clermont-Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, Clermont-Ferrand, France

April 2023

This review is a publication of the European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare for Ruminants & Equines. EURCAW Ruminants & Equines was designated by the European Commission through implementing decision of 6 May 2021, in accordance with Regulation 2017/625/EU.

Disclaimer

This review can be downloaded for free at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7685132>

Citation: Botreau, R., Lesimple, C., Brunet, V., & Veissier, I. (2023). Review – Environmental enrichment in ruminants and equines - Introduction. *EURCAW Ruminants & Equines*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7685132>

Each EURCAW Ruminants & Equines review provides background information on the biological relevance of the welfare topic. It then presents the most important key areas to focus on during welfare inspections, describes why welfare issues occur and lists specific animal-based indicators that can help official inspectors to identify these welfare issues. Finally, the review summarises good and better practices that can help to solve the previously described welfare issues, and deals with related legislative requirements.

EURCAW Ruminants & Equines produces its reviews according to internationally accepted scientific standards, which include an external peer review process. However, it cannot accept liability for any damage resulting from the use of the results of this study or the application of the advice contained in it.

info@eurcaw-ruminants-equines.eu

<https://www.eurcaw-ruminants-equines.eu/>

[@eurcaw_re](https://twitter.com/eurcaw_re)

Designated by
the EU Commission

Contents

1	Executive summary	4
2	Foreword	4
3	Definitions	5
4	Identification of animals' needs	7
5	Present situation	9
5.1	Cattle	9
5.2	Sheep and goats	9
5.3	Equines	10
5.4	Deer	10
5.5	Buffaloes	11
5.6	Camelids	11
5.7	Bison	11
6	Checking the efficiency of environmental enrichment	11
6.1	Use of an enrichment	12
6.2	Preference for and motivation to get an enrichment	12
6.3	Impact of an enrichment on animal welfare	13
7	Environmental enrichments: what and how?	14
7.1	Physical enrichments	14
7.2	Occupational enrichments	14
7.3	Sensory enrichments	14
7.4	Feeding enrichments	15
7.5	Relational enrichments	16
8	Designing environmental enrichments	17
8.1	Step 1 – Identification of potential enrichments	18
8.2	Step 2 – Assessment of benefits / drawbacks	18
8.2.1	Enrichment use and animals' preferences	18
8.2.2	Impact on animal welfare	18
8.3	Step 3 – Refinement of enrichments	19
9	Conclusions	19
10	Annexes	20
11	References	24

Preliminary note

The concept of environmental enrichment applies to any species. As far as possible, examples given in the present review concern ruminants or equines. When knowledge is lacking in ruminants or equines we mention findings obtained in other species.

1 Executive summary

In natural habitats, animals receive many stimuli that vary in place and time. In such habitats, they can express a wide range of behaviours that define the species' "behavioural repertoire". Farming or captive environments are designed to meet their basic biological needs (e.g. for rest, feeding), but are far less complex than natural habitats. Animals thus may not be able to express some of the behaviours from their repertoire and as a consequence experience boredom. The concept of environmental enrichment refers to a wide range of modifications to the environment of captive or farmed animals that offer adequate stimulation and facilitate the expression of highly motivated behaviour, thereby promoting positive emotions and improving animal welfare. Environmental enrichment can be divided into five (non-exclusive) categories: relational, feeding, occupational, physical and sensory enrichments. A good knowledge of the behaviour and the biology of the species is essential for the design of relevant enrichments. The benefits and drawbacks of enrichments need to be assessed in both short and long term by studying the use of enrichments in terms of occupancy value, the preference and motivation of animals to use them and the impact on welfare. To support positive animal welfare, high quality enrichment that engages animals over a long period of time should be seriously considered.

2 Foreword

Domestic ruminants and equines are kept in a wide range of environments with varying complexity, from individual housing in barren pens to rearing in large groups in semi-natural environments. The richness of the environment has an impact on animal welfare. EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* proposed to review the available knowledge on environmental enrichment for the species covered by the Centre. The first review introduces the issue of environmental enrichment in general: What does an enriched environment mean? What are the various types of enrichment and what are the main consequences of a poor vs. enriched environment? Then separate reviews address the various types of enrichment: occupational and physical enrichment; sensory and feeding enrichment; and relational enrichment (including the impact of the presence of conspecifics and that of other species including humans). The goal is to understand the underlying mechanisms and how they impact on the various animal types. Directive 98/58/EC for the protection of farmed animals mentions ethological (behavioural) needs, but not positive emotions or enrichment. Directive 2008/119/EC for the protection of farmed calves further specifies that calves must have visual and tactile contacts and must be kept in group from the age of 8 weeks. Directive 2010/63/EU for the protection of animals used for scientific purposes mentions enrichment, in reference to the expression of behaviour and the reduction of negative emotions (stress). For the purpose of EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* the reviews on enrichment will therefore mainly address enrichment relevant to behavioural or sensorial needs and will make no distinction between animals used for farming or scientific purposes.

3 Definitions

Natural habitats are often very rich: animals receive many stimuli that vary in place and time; they can express a wide range of behaviours, defining the so-called “behavioural repertoire” of their species. The behavioural repertoire includes various activities which can be species-specific (e.g. social interactions, sexual behaviour, foraging). It allows the species to be adapted to its habitat. Farmed or captive environments are designed to cover animals’ basic biological needs (e.g. for rest, for feeding), however they are far less complex than natural habitats. Despite generations of breeding in non-natural habitats, domestic, farmed and captive animals still display behaviours of their original repertoire (Sluyter & Van Oortmerssen, 2000). The possibility for the animal to perform such behaviours can be rewarding, apart from the strict fulfilment of its biological needs. For instance, in natural conditions young calves take their food by suckling their dam. Nutritional needs can be fulfilled in calves drinking milk from buckets; calves fed milk from buckets are nevertheless motivated to suck and they can redirect sucking towards inanimate objects (a dry teat for instance) or other calves (in so called ‘cross-sucking’) (Rushen & de Passillé, 1995). Behavioural needs refer to behaviours that are performed whatever the environment (Weeks & Nicol, 2006). Animals generally experience suffering when they cannot fulfil behavioural needs (Jensen & Toates, 1993). The term behavioural priority has been introduced to refer to a behaviour the animal is motivated to perform (e.g. in operant conditioning settings) (Nicol, 2011; Weeks & Nicol, 2006). The degree of suffering due to not performing the behaviour depends on the strength of its priority (measured by the amount of work the animal is ready to produce to obtain a reward). In addition to be denied the possibility to express some behaviours, animals may lack stimulation and experience boredom when they are in barren environments, which can manifest as stereotypies (Wemelsfelder, 1993).

It is now widely acknowledged that animals not only have biological needs but also behavioural and sensorial needs. Not expressing a behaviour for which there is a need results in frustration, with e.g. signs of stress or over-expression later when the behaviour is possible (‘rebound’ behaviour). In addition, some behaviours are particularly pleasant to animals and procure positive emotions, e.g. positive interactions with peers or the dam, play behaviour, having control on the environment (Mellor, 2016).

The concept of environmental enrichment refers to a wide range of modifications to the environment of captive or farmed animals that offer adequate stimulation and facilitate the expression of highly motivated behaviour thus promoting positive emotions and improving animals’ welfare.

Directive 98/58/EC for the protection of farmed animals mentions ethological (behavioural) needs, but not positive emotions or enrichment. Directive 2008/119/EC for the protection of farmed calves further specifies that calves must have visual and tactile contacts and must be kept in group from the age of 8 weeks. Directive 2010/63/EU for the protection of animals used for scientific purposes mentions enrichment, in reference to the expression of behaviour and the reduction of negative emotions (stress). For the purpose of EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* the

reviews on enrichment will therefore mainly address behavioural or sensorial needs and will make no distinction between animals used for farming or scientific purposes.

Environmental enrichment starts from “housing supplementation” with few elements added to very poor environments and can go up to rearing in complex environments close to natural habitats (Benefiel et al., 2005; Boissy et al., 2007; Duncan & Olsson, 2001; Newberry, 1995). Basic enrichments (“housing supplementation”) added to a poor environment may improve animal welfare but are insufficient to promote good animal welfare since the environment remains too constrained to allow the animals to express their full behavioural repertoire. For instance, groups of five calves housed in 9 m² slatted-floor pens are enriched compared to calves housed in individual crates because it facilitates social interactions, but overall it does not provide a rich environment.

Environmental enrichments may provide additional opportunities for different facets of the animal’s life, e.g. food-related, housing, social, spatial and / or cognitive exercise (Newberry, 1995). Environmental enrichments can be classified into five (non-exclusive) categories (adapted from Bloomsmith et al., 1991; Mandel et al., 2016):

- **physical enrichments** that include the complexity of the animal’s enclosure and the provision of additional elements (e.g. hiding places);
- **occupational enrichments** that promote physical and/or psychological activities by providing opportunities to exercise or to engage in cognitive tasks;
- **sensory enrichments**, designed to stimulate one or several senses of the animal, and include visual, auditory, olfactory, tactile and taste stimulations.
- **feeding enrichments** that promotes foraging and feeding behaviour by providing new or varied foods, or feed delivery methods or tools;
- **relational enrichments** that embrace social contacts, development of feeling safety, facilitation or learning in diverse situation and specific bonds with conspecifics or individuals of other species (including humans);

These categories are not exclusive: e.g. new food items can provide both a feeding and a sensory enrichment, a new food-delivery system can provide both a feeding and a cognitive enrichment, the possibility to see conspecifics can provide both a sensory (visual) and a relational enrichment.

Enrichment aims at improving the welfare of animals. Any solution nevertheless to improve welfare is not necessarily an enrichment. For instance, adjusting the diet of an animal to cover its metabolic needs cannot be considered an enrichment, especially if the animal does not perceive changes (e.g. micro-nutrient composition of a diet is not perceived by the animal in the short term at least). In turn any enrichment designed by humans may not improve animal welfare if it does not correspond to animal needs or preferences. Typically, enrichment should promote positive welfare and not only prevent negative welfare.

4 Identification of animals' needs

Enriching the environment requires facilitation of the animals' needs, which depends on their perceptual world (Rørvang & Nawroth, 2021; Uexküll & Kriszat, 2013). A good knowledge of the species, its behaviour and biology is thus essential to implement relevant enrichment (e.g. Würbel, 2009). Also needs may differ between individuals within species, depending for instance on their development stage. Examples are provided below. The species in the scope of EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* are herbivorous. In a natural habitat they spend a large proportion of the day eating grass, leaves, bushes etc. Depending on the resource availability, equines spend 60-75% (up to 80% for lactating mares) of their time feeding while slowly walking (1 step/s) (e.g. Waring, 2003). Feeding bouts are distributed throughout the 24-h period so that their gut remains relatively full. At pasture, cattle spend approximately 1/3 of their time grazing and 1/3 ruminating motionless in a quiet environment (Neave et al., 2021). In a comparative study on feeding behaviour, horses spent up to 3 times more grazing than sheep, but when adding rumination bouts of the sheep, the time spent feeding was similar (Dulphy et al., 1997). When fed with diets that can be rapidly ingested (like concentrate feed), the animals may develop abnormal behaviour (Aziz ur Rahman et al., 2019; Waters et al., 2002), as if they compensate for the lack of feeding behaviour. For instance, calves denied the possibility to eat solid foods spend more time in non-nutritive oral activities (Veissier et al., 1998). Under domestic or farming conditions, feeding conditions are often constrained in terms of distribution over time (restricted number of meals) and diversity (mostly single roughage and concentrates, and sometimes provided in a total mixed ration) (cattle: Gomez & Cook, 2010; horses: Thorne et al., 2005), leading to potential behavioural disorders (e.g. stereotypies, cattle: Seo et al., 1998; horses: Ninomiya et al., 2004). For both ruminants and equines, the provision of feeds that are slowly ingested, e.g. roughage, allows them to spend a large part of the day feeding. This may be even more important for equines (see below) due to their natural patterns of feeding behaviour. Ruminants should also benefit from a quiet place where they can ruminate undisturbed.

The social organisation, as can be observed in natural or semi-natural habitats, varies with species, but with a common trait: the majority of ruminants and equines are gregarious, living in social groups (except some reproductive males). Horses live in stable family groups (Waring, 2003). Young male horses form separate 'bachelor groups'. Donkeys may live in stable family groups as horses or in large female groups with males in close proximity (McDonnell, 1998). Cattle reside in large multi-female groups with their offspring, and small groups of young male or solitary males in close proximity (Bouissou et al., 2001). Goats and sheep are also organised into groups of related females with their offspring and groups of males, the size of the groups depending on the habitat, with larger groups in open habitat with a risk of predation (Shackleton & Shank, 1984). Deer species that are farmed such as red and fallow deer show seasonal sexual segregation typically with groups consisting of females and their offspring and a separate bachelor herd. These groups congregate during the reproduction period (Mysterud, 1998; Wang & Schreiber, 2001).

Social isolation is a source of stress for gregarious species (cattle: Rushen et al., 1999; goats and sheep: Price & Thos, 1980; rabbits: Chu et al., 2003; horses: Rivera et al., 2002) and can lead to the development of undesired behaviours (Benhajali et al., 2010; Costa et al., 2016; Visser et al., 2008). In order to alleviate these negative effects, social enrichments may be set up. In addition, in most species, the presence of adults with young animals improves the development of the behaviour and decreases the prevalence of abnormal behaviours, including stereotypies (horses: Henry et al., 2012; sheep: Nowak et al., 2018). Mixing animals i.e. changing the group composition, can also be stressful (Proudfoot & Habing, 2015). The impacts vary depending on the social organisation of the species and the development stage of the animals. Indeed repeatedly mixing of 11-15 months old heifers reduced stress but had the opposite effects on calves that were a few months old, probably due to the development of social behaviour around puberty (Boissy et al., 2001; Raussi et al., 2006; Veissier et al., 2001). Both isolation, mixing and overcrowding can induce social stress and may impair health (Proudfoot & Habing, 2015).

Some species, like sheep, show a high level of group behavioural synchronisation (social facilitation), so that enrichment may be more effective if it can be done at group level (allowing all animals to perform the same activity at the same time). Other species like goats display more individual behaviours, they are probably more likely to explore their environment alone and are considered more inquisitive.

The behavioural needs and time-budgets are often different between adults and young of the same species. In some species, play is a strictly juvenile behaviour under natural conditions (Burghardt, 2005; Waring, 2003) and is considered to help the ontogeny of behaviour. For instance, social play is crucial for the development of behaviour of horses (Waring, 2003) and cattle (Jensen et al., 1998). Play in adults is rarely observed and may have a different role from play in juveniles (Burghardt, 2005; Oliveira et al., 2010). In horses, the most playful adults are those responding more intensively to humans and to tactile stimulation, so that in these animals play can be interpreted as a sign of suboptimal welfare (Blois-Heulin et al., 2015; Hausberger et al., 2012). Enrichments stimulating play behaviour will therefore be of importance for young animals and not necessarily for adults.

5 Present situation

Among ruminants and equines in the European Union (EU), cattle and sheep largely dominate in terms of the number of animals, followed by goats, equines, deer, buffaloes and other animals (camelids and bison) (*Annexe 1*). Cattle by far predominate the other species in terms of equivalent Livestock Units (LSU) and number of farms (*Annexe 2*). The most current conditions for their management – especially housing – are described below.

5.1 Cattle

Bovines, almost entirely cattle, represent 79.4 million animals for 57.4 million LSU; they are distributed throughout the EU (*Annexe 2 & Annexe 4*, Eurostat, 2016). In the EU, most cattle are outdoors at pasture during the grazing season and indoors in winter. The duration of each period depends on weather conditions and grass availability. In Ireland where the oceanic climate makes grass growing for a large part of the year, beef cattle may overwinter outdoors or indoors (in colder regions and or to prevent 'poaching' of the grass) whereas dairy cattle overwinter indoors. By contrast, in Nordic countries cattle may only be kept outdoors for a few months, if at all. Zero grazing is also practiced in some EU member states, e.g. in Netherlands where canals surround pastures, cattle may be housed all year, mainly to avoid pollution by manure leaching. When indoors, cattle are generally housed in group pens, with a straw-yard or cubicles to rest. Tethering is decreasing in the EU and is most often seen in mountainous areas or in some countries (Germany, Poland). For beef bulls, straw-yards are more common than other types of housing and they are turned out onto pasture less often during summer. According to EU legislation calves can be housed in individual stalls, not tethered, up to 2 months of age. Calves from beef breeds are generally suckled by their dams: when outdoors, they are maintained in the same pasture as adult cows whereas indoors they can be grouped in pens and separated from the dams except for suckling (generally twice a day). Most dairy calves are separated from the dam soon after birth, they drink milk from buckets with or without a teat dispenser (bucket fixed with a teat or automatic milk feeder). The vast majority of dairy calves do not have outdoor access, they are kept in group pens at least after 2 months of age.

5.2 Sheep and goats

Sheep and goat farming, which represents just 3.6% of the total value of meat production in the EU, is considered to be the most vulnerable livestock sector (increasing aging and poor retention of farmers, health crises, attacks by predators, decline in sheep meat consumption) (European Parliament, 2018). Despite the low economical value of sheep and goat production there are currently about 75 million sheep and goats in the EU27 (85% sheep and 15% goats), often kept in economically vulnerable areas such as mountain regions, mainly in southern Europe (*Annexe 2, Annexe 3 & Annexe 5*, European Commission, 2022). In the sheep sector, meat is the most important production from an economic point of view, despite the fact that it is going through a phase of strong contraction due to the increase of dairy production, in response to consumer demand. In the goat sector, there is an increase in dairy products and exports of goats to third countries.

Overall, the sheep and goat supply chain is characterised by a marked heterogeneity of the farm type, with a predominance of extensive and semi-extensive farming, with some countries relying on intensive farming. Four types of farming systems may be described. In intensive farming systems, animals are kept indoor, with no grazing and rare access to an outdoor exercise area. In semi-intensive systems, animals are kept indoors but have access to outdoor paddocks or pasture during the day for a few months. In semi-extensive farming, animals are kept indoors overwinter, and at pasture during the rest of the year. Finally, in extensive systems, animals are kept almost permanently outdoors at pasture and generally benefit from natural shelters.

5.3 Equines

In Europe (EU and non-EU countries), the equid population is around 7 million of horses, ponies, mules and donkeys but figures are probably underestimated (Eurogroup4Animals, 2015). A significant proportion of equines are kept by private owners, non-farmers (which explains the difference with figures presented in *Annexe 2 & Annexe 6*). The European equine industry is divided into several sectors differing in terms of management and working constraints for the animal. Sport and leisure horses represent most of the population, followed by racehorses. The breeding, working and production horses are far less numerous. Donkeys are mostly distributed between leisure, equine assisted activities, working and production sectors. Mules are mostly used for leisure and working purposes. Strong differences exist between sectors concerning the housing, feeding and working conditions of equines.

Sport and racehorses as well as stallions are mostly housed (>80% of their time) in single boxes or tied in individual stalls with no or little access to social and spatial resources, they are fed two to three meals of high energy concentrate food per day and a limited amount of hay. A large proportion of these horses leave their stalls only for training and events, they are thus not allowed to exercise freely. Restrictions at social, spatial and feeding levels differ markedly compared to natural conditions. Leisure equines are more likely to be housed in groups, with or without daily access to paddocks or pastures. They are often fed larger amount of grass and roughage, with occasional provision of concentrate food. They may be involved in physically challenging activities. Production, breeding and working (draught) equines, including those used in tourism and equine assisted activities are mostly kept in fairly stable groups, outdoors with stabling/shelter in adverse weather conditions. They are mainly fed grass or roughage with concentrate supplementation when necessary. Breeding horses and those reared for meat (weaner) are mostly housed outdoors in more or less stable groups, with few physical constraints, whilst production horses reared for their blood (to produce hormones) or those reared for meat (fattener) may be subjected to conditions that restrict their behavioural activity. Working equines (including donkeys and mules) may undertake challenging physical activities.

5.4 Deer

According to the Federation of European Deer Farmers Associations (FEDFA, 2022), the EU has approximately 310,000 farmed deer, mainly fallow deer (76%), followed by red deer (20%) and Sika deer (4%) (*Annexe 8*). The figures are underestimated because FEDFA membership is on a voluntary basis and does not include all of EU27 countries (only 16 EU member states, of which

only 11 provide figures). Furthermore, reindeer are not in the scope of the FEDFA although they are farmed in Sweden (250,000 heads) and Finland (204,000 heads) (EFSA, 2012). Fallow, Red and Sika deer can be reared in artificial groups in fenced outdoor paddocks or in a more extensive form with natural groups and less human contact. They may be housed overwinter depending on climate and the age of the animals, indoor housing for mature deer is sometimes practiced but not recommended for welfare reasons (Hanlon & Griffin, 2022; Mattiello, 2009). Reindeer are managed in open-range systems in northern forests and mountains.

5.5 Buffaloes

The EU population of buffaloes represents less than 1% of the world population with about 460,000 head (Eurostat, 2019; FAO, 2013), mainly in Italy, Romania, Bulgaria, and Greece (*Annexe 7*). Farming systems can be extensive, but are mainly intensive, with animals loose housed with outdoor paddocks or with no access to pasture such as in Italy or in tied stalls such as in Romania and Bulgaria. In Greece, buffaloes are reared in small herds with access to pasture (Borghese, 2005).

5.6 Camelids

The number of camelids (camels, dromedaries, llamas, alpacas) kept in zoological gardens, circuses and farms is estimated at 5,000-6,000 animals in Europe (Faye, 2020). Camels can be used to produce meat, milk, wool or hides in farming systems or for cultural and recreational purposes (Faye, 2014). No information was found on how they are farmed.

5.7 Bison

No information was found on the number of farmed bison in the EU nor on enrichment. They will thus not be addressed in the EURCAW reviews on enrichment.

Farming conditions for ruminants and equines can vary from very restrictive housing (e.g. horses in individual stall with no opportunity for free physical exercise) to extensive production systems (e.g. sheep in large flocks on meadows with mixed vegetation). Restrictive environments do not allow animals to meet their behavioural needs as defined above. These gaps between animal needs and opportunities offered by the environment requires that the environment is enriched.

6 Checking the efficiency of environmental enrichment

Environmental enrichments should support positive behavioural, emotional and cognitive states and thus increase welfare. The expression of natural behaviour for which the animals are motivated is indeed likely to promote positive emotions (Boissy et al., 2007). If adapted to the needs of animals, enrichments should have beneficial effects. If not adapted, an enrichment may be inefficient (Stachurska et al., 2013) or even harmful (e.g. more stereotypic behaviours in presence of “toys” in horses, Luescher et al., 1998). In any case, it is necessary to check the efficiency of an enrichment before it is deployed. A combination of several components has to be

considered: Is the enrichment used by animals? Are animals motivated by the enrichment? Does the enrichment have either positive or negative impacts on the animals?

6.1 Use of an enrichment

A first step to determine the efficiency of an environmental enrichment is to assess whether or not it is used by the animals. Goats placed in an enriched environment (with haynets, chewing disks, platforms, logs, brushes) can, during the day, interact with the enrichments for 25% of their time (De Almeida et al, *in prep*) whereas horses spend little time interacting with non-edible enrichments (0.33% in Bulens et al., 2015; Jørgensen et al., 2011). The proportion of the population using the enrichment should also be considered (Wilson et al., 2002) since preferences may vary between individuals. The effectiveness of an enrichment may be considered lower if used a lot by a few individuals rather than scarcely but by all individuals. In case the enrichment is used by only a few animals, additional enrichments have to be considered to reach the other animals. How long the interest for an enrichment lasts (the 'occupancy value') must also be taken into consideration: the interest may be strong but short lasting for some items whereas the interest may not fade with time with other items (Mandel et al., 2016; Wilson et al., 2002). If the interest is short-lasting, the enrichment items should be replaced on a regular basis. However, active interaction with items is not essential for assessing the efficiency of enrichment, as no interaction can still reduce stress and improve welfare (e.g. humans often seek to be in natural environment with trees without physically interacting with it) (Decker et al, 2023).

6.2 Preference for and motivation to get an enrichment

An animal's preference for the type of enrichment can be measured by comparing their use in a free choice situation or by conducting preference tests with only one enrichment accessible at a time. When placed in a multi-enriched environment, goats spent 20.3% time using "climbing" enrichment vs. 2.8% time using brushes (de Almeida et al, *in prep*). When facing a choice in a preference test, calves prefer entering a room with a human brushing them than an empty room (Westerath et al., 2014). Dairy cows prefer automatic brushes to fixed ones (Gutmann, 2010), and brushes to scent release devices (Wilson et al., 2002). When given the choice, horses prefer having access to food or to a paddock with conspecifics, followed by the access to an empty paddock, and returning to their stall. Forced exercise conditions (similar to a treadmill) were avoided by horses (Lee et al., 2011). Duncan & Young (2002) showed that when given the choice, goats actively preferred mixed food rather than a single food. When trained to use a light switch, both adult sheep and calves chose to have longer periods of light vs. darkness (sheep: 77% of the day, calves: 67% of the day, Baldwin et al., 1981).

The motivation for an enrichment can be assessed by the work an animal is ready to perform to obtain it (e.g. Kilgour et al., 1991; Mendl & Paul, 2020). Comparing the motivation displayed towards several enrichments allows the identification of the most significant enrichment from the animal's point of view (Dawkins, 1990). For instance, horses are very motivated to access food (even when fed with an adequate diet) and to have contacts with conspecifics whereas access to a barren large enclosure is less important to them (Lee et al., 2011; Søndergaard et al., 2011). Calves also are very motivated to obtain full contact with conspecifics rather than head-only

contact (Holm et al., 2002). The frustration of not having enrichment can also be measured by the level of stress when the access to an enrichment is denied or by the over-expression of a previously prevented behaviour. For example, cortisol increases in fur-farmed minks when they are denied access to a water pool after they have been used to use it for 6 weeks (Mason et al., 2001), and cattle tethered indoors for 6 days over-express locomotion (running, jumping) when moved to a paddock (Nakayama & Ninomiya, 2018).

6.3 Impact of an enrichment on animal welfare

The ultimate aim of environmental enrichment is to improve animal welfare. It is therefore crucial to evaluate the impact of enrichments on the animals' behaviour, stress level, health or overall fitness. Adding platforms was shown to have positive impacts on feeding, resting and social behaviour of goats (Aschwanden et al., 2009). In turkeys, the addition of environmental enrichment was tested in order to replace the conventional solution of "beak trimming" to prevent injuries. The results showed that adding straw and platforms decreased the proportion of injured animals in both males and females (Mirabito & Michel, 2003). The results are nevertheless not always positive: when adding platforms in rabbits' environment, the behavioural repertoire was closer to the natural one, but injuries were more frequent (Trocino et al., 2019), suggesting that the design of platforms or their access should be improved. In horses, providing a mobile food delivery system for concentrates increased the time spent eating, but it was also associated with the development of frustration and stereotypic behaviours (Goodwin et al., 2007). On the contrary, using slow-feeders (Rochais et al., 2018) or increasing hay diversity (Goodwin et al., 2002; Thorne et al., 2005) increased the time spent feeding, resting and decreased the prevalence of stereotypic behaviours. Impacts on the behavioural and physiological reactivity of animals can also be observed. For instance, heifers that regularly meet other heifers react less to unusual stimuli and habituate to them more quickly than heifers that always stay with the same pen mates, they also react less (i.e. release less cortisol) to a pharmacological challenge (CRF injection to stimulate the release of cortisol in blood) suggesting a lower chronic stress state (Raussi et al. 2006).

It is of prime importance to comprehensively assess the impact of an enrichment on animals in all animal welfare dimensions, to ensure that potential negative impacts are identified. Focusing on the occupancy value, differentiating between short-term (e.g. exploration of a new device) and longer term effects (e.g. prolonged use of a device, variety of behaviours expressed for a long period) will improve the effectiveness and beneficial impacts on animals.

7 Environmental enrichments: what and how?

Examples of enrichments used in farming conditions are provided below. The usefulness of such enrichments depends on the rearing conditions of animals: environments such as pastures in semi-natural habitats with a variety of plants, including bushes and trees may not need to be enriched whereas indoor housing in barren pens certainly requires enrichments.

7.1 Physical enrichments

Physical enrichments consist of providing more space and additional elements to offer more diversity of the environment and more freedom of behaviour.

The environment has to provide sufficient space for animals to avoid or escape in case of social conflict. The addition of supplementary space, either by increasing the size of the enclosure (cattle: Veissier et al., 2008; horses: Lesimple et al., 2020; Visser et al., 2008) or by adding elements such as platforms (goats: Aschwanden et al., 2009; rabbits: Trocino et al., 2019) decreases agonistic and stereotypic behaviours and increases the time spent feeding and the resting quality (time and posture). Depending on the species' needs, the provision of nesting material, "refuge" areas or observation points increases positive social relationships and the time spent resting, improves feeding behaviour, and decreases aggression and stereotypic / abnormal behaviours (Aschwanden et al., 2009; Proudfoot et al., 2014).

7.2 Occupational enrichments

The possibility for the animals to engage in physical or cognitive activities when reared in farmed or domestic conditions can be limited, whilst it is considered that captive/domestic animals should be given opportunities for stimulating activities comparable to those performed by their wild counterparts (Spinka & Wemelsfelder, n.d.; Swaisgood & Shepherdson, 2008). Occupational enrichments provide the opportunity to perform biologically relevant physical or cognitive tasks. Allowing animals reared indoors to access an outdoor area increases the possibilities for locomotion and exploration (cattle: Castro et al., 2011; Veissier et al., 2008; horses: Lesimple et al., 2011, 2019) and reduces body and joint lesions (Keil et al., 2006; Loberg et al., 2004; Popescu et al., 2013; Regula et al., 2004). Occupational enrichment can also be achieved by stimulating the cognitive abilities of the farmed / captive animals by making them "work" to access a resource thanks to instrumental learning devices (e.g. goats: Langbein et al., 2009; horses: Lee et al., 2011). Including small challenges in the animals' daily environment may help preserve their psychological wellness (Rasmussen et al., 2020). In addition, having to work to access a resource gives control on the environment, which is perceived positively by animals (Greiveldinger et al., 2009).

7.3 Sensory enrichments

Sensory enrichment may include a wide range of stimuli that affect one or several senses (Bloomsmith et al., 1991; Wells, 2009). Not all stimuli constitute appropriate enrichment. Indeed, loud and unnatural noises like metallic sounds, or artificial light may be perceived negatively by animals (e.g. human shouting: Pajor et al., 2000; noise: Waynert et al., 1999).

Music diffusion in barns was tested with mixed results (reviewed by Ciborowska et al., 2021). Dairy cows are more willing to approach milking systems in the presence of music (country music in this study) (Uetake et al., 1997), and the diffusion of auditory stimuli (country and classical music, audiobooks) decreases the prevalence of stereotypic behaviours (Crouch et al., 2019). The exposure to slow music seems to have positive consequences (reduced stress in dogs: Bowman et al., 2015; better sleep and decrease stereotypic behaviours in horses: Hartman & Greening, 2019, Huo et al., 2021), with variations between species: increased performance in pigs (Ekachai & Vajrabukka, 1994) and koi carp (Vasanthi et al., 2003), no impact on rats (Pfaff & Stecker, 1976) or cows (Kıyıcı et al., 2013) (see Alworth & Buerkle, 2013; Wells, 2009 for reviews). In contrast, silence may be preferred to music by some animals: tamarins and marmoset monkeys prefer silence to slow or fast music (McDermott & Hauser, 2007) and cows produce less milk when exposed to various music (country, rock, opera, jazz, reggae, pop, lullaby, classical, rap, heavy metal, and hip-hop) (Kemp, 2020). Despite some beneficial effects on ruminants' behaviour, the use of music as an enrichment remains to be further investigated. The diffusion of odours in the environment can impact the animals' behaviour either by increasing activity (e.g. Powell, 1995) or on the contrary by having an anxiolytic / calming effect (e.g. Bradshaw et al., 1998; Graham et al., 2005). The impacts differ between odours and species, and have to be cautiously checked before application. The application of flavour in the food (concentrates : Goodwin et al., 2005) or water (Van Diest et al., 2021) impacts consumption by the animals, e.g. increased consumption in case of sweet flavours (horses: Goodwin et al., 2005). In addition, animals often seek for diversity in food flavour (active choice for food diversity: sheep: Provenza et al., 1996; horses: Thorne et al., 2005, see Favreau-Peigne et al 2013 for review). Animals are also able to discriminate between foods of different nutritional characteristics and to adapt their behaviour accordingly e.g. when fed rapidly digestible food in the morning, lambs prefer slowly digestible food in the evening (Early & Provenza, 1998). Sensory enrichment could also include visual stimulation (e.g. pictures) and tactile stimulation (e.g. brushes).

7.4 Feeding enrichments

Feeding enrichments should provide the animal with food diversity as well as the opportunity to spend more time feeding (e.g. by providing roughage). Different strategies can be adopted, e.g. providing several types of roughage at the same time or alternating between roughages (Garrett et al., 2021; Hutchings et al., 2003; Meagher et al., 2017; Thorne et al., 2005), increasing the access time or changing the temporal distribution of access to forage (Benhajali et al., 2008) or spacing out the feeding points to enlarge the individual feeding space (DeVries et al., 2004). These strategies increase the time spent eating/foraging, reduce aggressivity, decrease the time spent performing abnormal / stereotypic behaviours (DeVries et al., 2004). They can also reduce health disorders (colic / laminitis: Jonsson & Egenvall, 2006; Tinker et al., 1997). In addition to the provision of supplementary roughage, favouring edible litters can facilitate a more natural pattern of feeding behaviour (Baumgartner et al., 2020) and decrease the prevalence of stereotypic / abnormal behaviours (Tuytens, 2005).

7.5 Relational enrichments

Relational enrichment refers to contacts and bonds with partners of the same or different species. It has many advantages: not only interactions between preferential animals can provide positive emotions but also the presence of partners can favour a feeling of safety, help coping with stressors, facilitate learning (by imitation), and improve emotionality or cognitive traits (Veissier et al., 1998). Group housing improves animals' social skills (Costa et al., 2016; Fureix et al., 2012), and is beneficial provided that attention is paid to group composition and maintaining stability over time. On the contrary, social instability or inappropriate group composition can induce stress-related behaviours and increase aggression (Christensen et al., 2011; Fureix et al., 2012; Proudfoot & Habing, 2015). In case of individual housing, favouring physical and visual contacts with close neighbours (e.g. by open stalls, grid, mirrors) results in cattle being calmer (Piller et al., 1999) and horses displaying less stereotypic behaviours and also being calmer (Cooper et al., 2000; Lesimple et al., 2019; McAfee et al., 2002). If contact with conspecifics is not possible, providing contacts with individuals from other species (sometimes referred to as 'stable companions') may mimic social interactions. For example, a lamb can be adopted by a goat and a kid by a ewe (Kendrick et al., 1998). Finally, promoting positive interactions between animals and their handlers decrease stress related to human presence and to handling, reassure animals and can generate positive emotions (cattle: Lürzel et al., 2016; goats: Boivin & Braastad, 1996; horses: Fureix et al., 2009, Rault et al., 2018).

Furthermore, selecting a distribution modality to better align with the species' natural feeding time-budget can improve welfare. For instance, using tools such as hay nets or slow-feeders for roughage delivery increases the time spent feeding (Correa et al., 2020; Rochais et al., 2018).

The possibility to choose enrichments – whatever their type – seems of high value. Not only does choice increase the probability to obtain a desirable resource and allow some control over their environment, the act of choosing *per se* seems rewarding. Compared to being offered a desirable resource, the act of choosing is preferred by monkeys (Suzuki, 1999; Perdue et al., 2014). In humans choosing seems highly rewarding, with brain activity modified in regions involved in reward processing (Arana et al., 2003; Sharot et al., 2009; Leotti and Delgado, 2011). However, there is a lack of research concerning the impact of choice of enrichments on ruminants and equines.

For detailed knowledge about the different types of enrichment in ruminants and equines, see reviews on physical and occupational enrichment (Botreau et al., 2023), sensory and feeding enrichment (Ginane & Rørvang, 2023) and relational enrichment (de Oliveira & Boivin, 2023).

8 Designing environmental enrichments

We propose a 3-step approach for the design of enrichments (*Figure 1*):

1. identification of potential enrichments
2. assessment of benefits and drawbacks of enrichments
3. refinement of enrichments

This approach is suggested to those producing knowledge on enrichment or testing enrichment solutions. Policy-makers should check that the enrichment solutions recommended on farms have been validated according to such an approach. We do not expect official inspectors to use such an approach during farm inspections.

Figure 1: 3-step approach for the design of enrichments

8.1 Step 1 – Identification of potential enrichments

A first step is to identify the needs of animals. This is often done by considering the “natural” niche of animals and their behavioural repertoire depending on their development stage. The literature on preferences, for various components of the environment, of the different types of herbivore livestock, will be helpful as well as to identify potential enrichments. The actual environment of animals should then be analysed to identify potential deficiencies that prevent the fulfilment of behavioural or sensorial needs. For instance, gregarious animals housed individually probably lack the company of other animals. Then the means to enrich the environment can be proposed. For instance, pair or group housing for gregarious animals. Such an exercise should be performed regarding the suitability of the environment to implement the relevant enrichment type(s): relational, occupational and cognitive, physical, sensorial, feeding enrichment. A proposed enrichment can include one or more items to cover several components of the environment.

8.2 Step 2 – Assessment of benefits / drawbacks

8.2.1 *Enrichment use and animals' preferences*

- Measuring the time spent using the enrichment, including changes over time
- Measuring the proportion of animals using the enrichment
- Identifying the type of interactions with the enrichment and between individuals
- Conducting choice tests to identify the preferences of the animals
- Measuring the work an animal is willing to produce to get an enrichment or measuring potential signs of frustration in absence of the enrichment

8.2.2 *Impact on animal welfare*

- Evaluating changes in behaviour: reduction of undesirable behaviours (e.g. stereotypic behaviours, aggression) and increase of positive behaviours (e.g. exploration, play in young animals, resting)
- Evaluating the impact on behavioural reactivity (towards new environment or human for example)
- Evaluating the impact on physiological parameters, especially chronic stress (e.g. activity of the corticotropic axis)
- Evaluating the impact on health status (e.g. increased risk of injuries, spread of diseases)
- Evaluating the impacts on production when appropriate (e.g. growth or milk or production)

The use of an enrichment use, the preferences and motivations of the animals and the impact on animal welfare must be assessed in both the short and long term. The overall impact of an enrichment must be positive. In some cases, this may require trade-offs between positive and negative effects (e.g. positive effects on activity, reduction of stereotypies and improvement of cognitive abilities but some risk of injury).

8.3 Step 3 – Refinement of enrichments

The assessment of the impacts of an enrichment can help to refine its implementation. Observing how animals use an enrichment can help to improve its design and functionality. Detection of drawbacks should result in design solutions. Then a feedback to Step 2 is required to test the appropriateness of the refined enrichment.

In addition, the impact of an enrichment can help to improve the understanding of the needs of species or individuals. For instance, although cattle are gregarious animals, it seems that their need to interact with social partners varies with age, e.g. young calves preferring stable partnerships. In that case, a feedback to Step 1 is required to refine needs and/or knowledge on the environment so as to propose a more adequate enrichment. The refinement may differ between individuals or groups of individuals of similar characteristics.

9 Conclusions

Farm animals often live in environments that are far simpler than their natural habitat would be. This can result in a lack of stimulation and restrict their behaviours. Enrichments should help to reduce the gap between farmed and natural environments in terms of stimulation and behavioural opportunities. When investigating the impact of enrichments on animals, it is crucial to adopt the animals' point of view by matching the enrichments to their behavioural priorities and needs and assess the long-term consequences. Both benefits and drawbacks should be taken into account to ensure that the final balance is positive to animals.

10 Annexes

Annexe 1: Estimated percentage of captive ruminants and equines in EU27 (in heads, UK not included). Data for equines, deer, buffaloes and camelids are approximative and may be underestimated. Data for bison and other ruminant species are not available and thus not represented. Wild populations are excluded. Sources: British Equestrian Trade Association, 2019; EFSA, 2012; Eurogroup4Animals, 2015; Eurostat, 2019; Faye, 2020; FEDFA, 2022.

Annexe 2: Number of animals (heads and LSU) reared in farms and number of farms in EU27 (UK not included) in 2016, data from the agricultural census. Source: Eurostat, 2016.

LIVE ANIMALS IN TOTAL EU27	Equines	Bovines (including buffaloes)	Sheep	Goats
No. (per head)	2 583 390	79 361 330	63 311 060	11 399 440
No. LSU ¹	2 066 710	57 433 300	6 331 110	1 139 940
No. farms	671 160	1 925 480	715 460	378 420

¹ LSU: Livestock Unit

Annexe 4: Geographical distribution of cattle in EU27, year: 2016, unit: thousands of heads. Source: Eurostat, annual data.

Annexe 3: Geographical distribution of sheep in EU27, year: 2016, unit: heads. Source: Eurostat, agricultural census.

Annexe 5: Geographical distribution of goats in EU27, year: 2016, unit: heads. Source: Eurostat, agricultural census.

Annexe 6: Geographical distribution of equines in EU27, year: 2016, unit: heads. Source: Eurostat, agricultural census.

Annexe 8: Geographical distribution of deer (fallow deer, red deer, Sika deer and reindeer) in EU27, approximative figures, year: estimations covering the 2010-2022 period, unit: heads. Sources: FEDFA (2022) and EFSA (2012).

Annexe 7: Geographical distribution of buffaloes in EU27, year: 2015, unit: thousands of heads. Source: Eurostat, annual data.

11 References

- Alworth, L. C., & Buerkle, S. C. (2013). The effects of music on animal physiology, behavior and welfare. *Lab Animal*, 42(2), 54–61. <https://doi.org/10.1038/labanim.162>
- Arana F. S., Parkinson J. A., Hinton E., Holland A. J., Owen A. M., & Roberts A. C. (2003). Dissociable contributions of the human amygdala and orbitofrontal cortex to incentive motivation and goal selection. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 23, 9632–9638. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.23-29-09632.2003>
- Aschwanden, J., Gygax, L., Wechsler, B., & Keil, N. M. (2009). Loose housing of small goat groups: Influence of visual cover and elevated levels on feeding, resting and agonistic behaviour. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 119(3–4), 171–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2009.04.005>
- Aziz ur Rahman, M., Xia, C., Ji, L., Cao, B., & Su, H. (2019). Nutrient intake, feeding patterns, and abnormal behavior of growing bulls fed different concentrate levels and a single fiber source (corn stover silage). *Journal of Veterinary Behavior*, 33, 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jveb.2019.03.003>
- Baldwin, B. A., Start, I. B., & Cross, B. A. (1981). Sensory reinforcement and illumination preference in sheep and calves. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B. Biological Sciences*, 211(1185), 513–526. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.1981.0020>
- Baumgartner, M., Boisson, T., Erhard, M. H., & Zeitler-Feicht, M. H. (2020). Common Feeding Practices Pose A Risk to the Welfare of Horses When Kept on Non-Edible Bedding. *Animals*, 10(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10030411>
- Benefiel, A. C., Dong, W. K., & Greenough, W. T. (2005). Mandatory “Enriched” Housing of Laboratory Animals: The Need for Evidence-based Evaluation. *ILAR Journal*, 46(2), 95–105. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ilar.46.2.95>
- Benhajali, H., Richard-Yris, M.-A., Ezzaouia, M., Charfi, F., & Hausberger, M. (2010). Reproductive status and stereotypies in breeding mares: A brief report. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 128(1–4), 64–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2010.09.007>
- Benhajali, H., Richard-Yris, M.-A., Leroux, M., Ezzaouia, M., Charfi, F., & Hausberger, M. (2008). A note on the time budget and social behaviour of densely housed horses. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 112(1–2), 196–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2007.08.007>
- Blois-Heulin, C., Rochais, C., Camus, S., Fureix, C., Lemasson, A., Lunel, C., Bezard, E., & Hausberger, M. (2015). Animal Welfare: Could Adult Play be a False Friend? *Animal Behavior and Cognition*, 2(2), 156–185. <https://doi.org/10.12966/abc.05.04.2015>
- Bloomsmith, M. A., Brent, L. Y., & Schapiro, S. J. (1991). Guidelines for developing and managing an environmental enrichment program for nonhuman-primates. *Laboratory Animal Science*, 41(4), 372–377.
- Boissy, A., Manteuffel, G., Jensen, M. B., Moe, R. O., Spruijt, B., Keeling, L. J., Winckler, C., Forkman, B., Dimitrov, I., Langbein, J., Bakken, M., Veissier, I., & Aubert, A. (2007). Assessment of positive emotions in animals to improve their welfare. *Physiology & Behavior*, 92(3), 375–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2007.02.003>
- Boissy, A., Veissier, I., & Roussel, S. (2001). Behavioural Reactivity Affected by Chronic Stress: An Experimental Approach in Calves Submitted to Environmental Instability. *Animal Welfare*, 10, 175–185.
- Boivin, X., & Braastad, B. O. (1996). Effects of handling during temporary isolation after early weaning on goat kids’ later response to humans. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 48(1), 61–71. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(95\)01019-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(95)01019-X)
- Borghese, A. (2005). *Buffalo production and research*. REU Technical Series, 67. 321. <https://www.fao.org/3/ah847e/ah847e00.htm>

- Botreau, R., Brunet, V., & Lesimple, C. (2023)^b. Review – Physical and occupational enrichment in ruminants and equines. *EURCAW Ruminants & Equines*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7687759>
- Bouissou, M.-F., Boissy, A., Le Neindre, P. & Veissier, I. (2001). The social behaviour of cattle. In L. J. Keeling & H. W. Gonyou (Eds), *Social Behaviour in Farm Animals*. CABI Publishing. 33. <https://ci.nii.ac.jp/naid/10021222673/>
- Bowman, A., Scottish SPCA, Dowell, F. J., & Evans, N. P. (2015). 'Four Seasons' in an animal rescue centre; classical music reduces environmental stress in kennelled dogs. *Physiology & Behavior*, 143, 70–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2015.02.035>
- Bradshaw, R. H., Marchant, J. N., Meredith, M. J., & Broom, D. M. (1998). Effects of Lavender Straw on Stress and Travel Sickness in Pigs. *The Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*, 4(3), 271–275. <https://doi.org/10.1089/acm.1998.4.3-271>
- British Equestrian Trade Association. (2019). *British Equestrian Trade Association—National Equestrian Survey 2019 provides optimistic view of industry*. <https://www.beta-uk.org/pages/news-amp-events/news/national-equestrian-survey-2019-provides-optimistic-view-of-industry.php?searchresult=1&sstring=national+survey+2019>
- Bulens, A., Dams, A., Van Beirendonck, S., Van Thielen, J., & Driessen, B. (2015). A preliminary study on the long-term interest of horses in ropes and Jolly Balls. *Journal of Veterinary Behavior*, 10(1), 83–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jveb.2014.08.003>
- Burghardt, G. M. (2005). *The Genesis of Animal Play: Testing the Limits*. MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/3229.001.0001>
- Castro, I. M. L., Gygax, L., Wechsler, B., & Hauser, R. (2011). Increasing the interval between winter outdoor exercise aggravates agonistic interactions in Hérens cows kept in tie-stalls. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 129(2), 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2010.11.003>
- Christensen, J., Sondergaard, E., Thodberg, K., & Halekoh, U. (2011). Effects of repeated regrouping on horse behaviour and injuries. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 133(3-4), 199–206. <https://doi.org/DOI:10.1016/j.applanim.2011.05.013>
- Chu, L., Garner, J., & Mench, J. (2003). A behavioral comparison of New Zealand White rabbits (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) housed individually or in pairs in conventional laboratory cages. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 85(1-2), 121-139. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1016/j.applanim.2003.09.011> | Elsevier Enhanced Reader
- Ciborowska, P., Michalczyk, M., & Bień, D. (2021). The Effect of Music on Livestock: Cattle, Poultry and Pigs. *Animals*, 11(12), Article 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani1123572>
- Cooper, J. J., McDonald, L., & Mills, D. S. (2000). The effect of increasing visual horizons on stereotypic weaving: Implications for the social housing of stabled horses. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 69(1), 67–83. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(00\)00115-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(00)00115-5)
- Correa, M. G., Rodrigues e Silva, C. F., Dias, L. A., da Silva Rocha Junior, S., Thomes, F. R., Alberto do Lago, L., de Mattos Carvalho, A., & Faleiros, R. R. (2020). Welfare benefits after the implementation of slow-feeder hay bags for stabled horses. *Journal of Veterinary Behavior*, 38, 61–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jveb.2020.05.010>
- Costa, J. H. C., von Keyserlingk, M. A. G., & Weary, D. M. (2016). Invited review: Effects of group housing of dairy calves on behavior, cognition, performance, and health. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 99(4), 2453–2467. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-10144>
- Crouch, K., Evans, B., & Montrose, V. T. (2019). *The Effects of Auditory Enrichment on the Behaviour of Dairy Cows (Bos taurus)*. *British Society of Animal Science Annual Conference 2019*.
- Dawkins, M. S. (1990). From an animal's point of view: Motivation, fitness, and animal welfare. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 13(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X00077104>

- de Oliveira, D., & Boivin, X. (2023). Review – Relational enrichment in ruminants and equines. *EURCAW Ruminants & Equines*. Manuscript in preparation.
- Decker, S., Lavery, J. M., & Mason, G. J. (2023). Don't use it? Don't lose it! Why active use is not required for stimuli, resources or "enrichments" to have welfare value. *Zoo Biology*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/zoo.21756>
- DeVries, T. J., von Keyserlingk, M. A. G., & Weary, D. M. (2004). Effect of Feeding Space on the Inter-Cow Distance, Aggression, and Feeding Behavior of Free-Stall Housed Lactating Dairy Cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 87(5), 1432–1438. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(04\)73293-2](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(04)73293-2)
- Dulphy, J. P., Martin-Rosset, W., Dubroeuq, H., Ballet, J. M., Detour, A., & Jailler, M. (1997). Compared feeding patterns in ad libitum intake of dry forages by horses and sheep. *Livestock Production Science*, 52(1), 49–56. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-6226\(97\)00113-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-6226(97)00113-9)
- Duncan, A., & Young, S. (2002). Can goats learn about foods through conditioned food aversions and preferences when multiple food options are simultaneously available? *Journal of Animal Science*, 80(8), 2091–2098. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ansci/80.8.2091>
- Duncan, I., & Olsson, I. (2001). Environmental enrichment: From flawed concept to pseudo science. *Proceedings of the 35th Congress of the Society for Applied Ethology*, 73.
- Early, D. M., & Provenza, F. D. (1998). Food flavor and nutritional characteristics alter dynamics of food preference in lambs. *Journal of Animal Science*, 76(3), 728–734. <https://doi.org/10.2527/1998.763728x>
- EFSA. (2012). Technical hearing on the hazards to be covered by inspection of meat from farmed game. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 9(12), 24. <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2012.EN-376>
- Ekachat, K., & Vajrabukka, C. (1994). Effect of Music Rhythm on Growth Performance of Growing Pigs. *Agriculture and Natural Resources*, 28(4), Article 4.
- Eurogroup4Animals. (2015). *Removing the Blinkers: The Health and Welfare of European Equidae in 2015* (p. 123). https://www.eurogroupforanimals.org/files/eurogroupforanimals/2020-02/EU-Equine-Report-Removing-the-Blinkers_0.pdf
- European Commission. (2022). *Lamb, mutton and goatmeat*. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/animal-products/lamb-mutton-and-goatmeat_en
- European Parliament. (2018). *Report on the current situation and future prospects for the sheep and goat sectors in the EU | A8-0064/2018*. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-8-2018-0064_EN.html
- Eurostat. (2016). *Main livestock indicators by NUTS 2 regions*. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EF_LSK_MAIN/default/table?lang=en&category=agr.ef.ef_livestock
- Eurostat. (2019). *Database—Eurostat*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/data/database>
- FAO. (2013). *Dairy production and products: Buffaloes*. <https://www.fao.org/dairy-production-products/production/dairy-animals/buffaloes/en/>
- Favreau-Peigné, A., Baumont, R., & Ginane, C. (2013). Food sensory characteristics: Their unconsidered roles in the feeding behaviour of domestic ruminants. *Animal*, 7(5), 806–813. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731112002145>
- Faye, B. (2014). The Camel Today: Assets and Potentials. *Anthropozoologica*, 49(2), 167–176. <https://doi.org/10.5252/az2014n2a01>
- Faye, B. (2020). How many large camelids in the world? A synthetic analysis of the world camel demographic changes. *Pastoralism*, 10(1), 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13570-020-00176-z>
- FEDFA. (2022). The Federation of European Deer Farmers Associations. *FEDFA*. <https://www.fedfa.com/fedfa-members/>

- Fureix, C., Bourjade, M., Henry, S., Sankey, C., & Hausberger, M. (2012). Exploring aggression regulation in managed groups of horses *Equus caballus*. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *138*(3), 216–228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2012.02.009>
- Fureix, C., Jago, P., Sankey, C., & Hausberger, M. (2009). How horses (*Equus caballus*) see the world: Humans as significant “objects”. *Animal Cognition*, *12*(4), 643–654. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10071-009-0223-2>
- Garrett, K., Beck, M. R., Marshall, C. J., Maxwell, T. M. R., Logan, C. M., Greer, A. W., & Gregorini, P. (2021). Varied diets: Implications for lamb performance, rumen characteristics, total antioxidant status, and welfare. *Journal of Animal Science*, *99*(12), skab334. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jas/skab334>
- Ginane, C., & Rørvang, M.V. (2023). Review – Sensory and feeding enrichment in ruminants and equines. *EURCAW Ruminants & Equines*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7687769>
- Gomez, A., & Cook, N. (2010). Time budgets of lactating dairy cattle in commercial freestall herds. *Journal of Dairy Science*, *93*(12), 5772–5781. <https://doi.org/DOI:10.3168/jds.2010-3436>
- Goodwin, D., Davidson, H. P. B., & Harris, P. (2002). Foraging enrichment for stabled horses: Effects on behaviour and selection. *Equine Veterinary Journal*, *34*(7), 686–691. <https://doi.org/10.2746/042516402776250450>
- Goodwin, D., Davidson, H. P. B., & Harris, P. (2005). Selection and acceptance of flavours in concentrate diets for stabled horses. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *95*(3–4), 223–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2005.04.007>
- Goodwin, D., Davidson, H. P. B., & Harris, P. (2007). A note on behaviour of stabled horses with foraging devices in mangers and buckets. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *105*(1–3), 238–243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2006.05.018>
- Graham, L., Wells, D. L., & Hepper, P. G. (2005). The influence of olfactory stimulation on the behaviour of dogs housed in a rescue shelter. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *91*(1), 143–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2004.08.024>
- Greiveldinger, L., Veissier, I., & Boissy, A. (2009). Behavioural and physiological responses of lambs to controllable vs. uncontrollable aversive events. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, *34*, 805–814.
- Gutmann, A. (2010). Verhalten von Milchkühen bei der Nutzung von fixen gegenüber rotierenden Bürsten. *Proceedings of the 24th Internationale Gesellschaft Für Nutztierhaltung Conference*, 78–81. <http://www.animal-health-online.de/gross/wp-content/uploads/2010/06/24IGN-Tagung2010.pdf#page=80>
- Hanlon, A., & Griffin, L. (2022). Chapter 10: Red Deer. In J. Webster & J. Margerison (Eds), *Management and Welfare of Farm Animals: The UFAW Farm Handbook*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Harris, P. (2005). Nutrition, behaviour and the role of supplements for calming horses: The veterinarian’s dilemma. *The Veterinary Journal*, *170*(1), 10–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tvjl.2004.08.007>
- Hartman, N., & Greening, L. M. (2019). A Preliminary Study Investigating the Influence of Auditory Stimulation on the Occurrence of Nocturnal Equine Sleep-Related Behavior in Stabled Horses. *Journal of Equine Veterinary Science*, *82*, 102782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jevs.2019.07.003>
- Hausberger, M., Fureix, C., Bourjade, M., Wessel-Robert, S., & Richard-Yris, M.-A. (2012). On the significance of adult play: What does social play tell us about adult horse welfare? *Naturwissenschaften*, *99*(4), 291–302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00114-012-0902-8>
- Henry, S., Zanella, A. J., Sankey, C., Richard-Yris, M.-A., Marko, A., & Hausberger, M. (2012). Adults may be used to alleviate weaning stress in domestic foals (*Equus caballus*). *Physiology & Behavior*, *106*(4), 428–438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2012.02.025>
- Holm, L., Bak Jensen, M., & Jepsen, L. (2002). Calves’ motivation for access to two different types of social contact measured by operant conditioning. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *79*(3), 175–194. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(02\)00137-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(02)00137-5)

- Huo, X., Wongkwanklom, M., Phonraksa, T., & Na-Lampang, P. (2021). Effects of playing classical music on behavior of stabled horses. *Veterinary Integrative Sciences*, 19(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.12982/VIS.2021.023>
- Hutchings, M. R., Athanasiadou, S., Kyriazakis, I., & Gordon, I. J. (2003). Can animals use foraging behaviour to combat parasites? *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 62(2), 361–370. <https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS2003243>
- Jensen, P., & Toates, F. (1993). Who Needs Behavioral Needs—Motivational Aspects of the Needs of Animals. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 37(2), 161–181. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(93\)90108-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(93)90108-2)
- Jensen, M. B., Vestergaard, K. S., & Krohn, C. C. (1998). Play behaviour in dairy calves kept in pens: The effect of social contact and space allowance. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 56(2), 97–108. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(97\)00106-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(97)00106-8)
- Jonsson, H., & Egenvall, A. (2006). Prevalence of gastric ulceration in Swedish Standardbreds in race training. *Equine Veterinary Journal*, 38(3), 209–213. <https://doi.org/10.2746/042516406776866390>
- Jørgensen, G. H. M., Liestøl, S. H.-O., & Bøe, K. E. (2011). Effects of enrichment items on activity and social interactions in domestic horses (*Equus caballus*). *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 129(2–4), 100–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2010.11.004>
- Keil, N. M., Wiederkehr, T. U., Friedli, K., & Wechsler, B. (2006). Effects of frequency and duration of outdoor exercise on the prevalence of hock lesions in tied Swiss dairy cows. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 74(2), 142–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2005.11.005>
- Kemp, A. (2020). *The Effects of Music on Dairy Production*. 23.
- Kendrick, K. M., Hinton, M. R., Atkins, K., Haupt, M. A., & Skinner, J. D. (1998). Mothers determine sexual preferences. *Nature*, 395(6699), 229–230. <https://doi.org/10.1038/26129>
- Kilgour, R., Foster, T., Temple, W., & Matthews, L. (1991). Operant technology applied to solving farm animals problems. An assessment. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 30(1-2), 141–166. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(91\)90092-C](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(91)90092-C)
- Kıyıcı, J. M., Koçyığıt, R., & Tüzemen, N. (2013). The effect of classical music on milk production, milk components and milking characteristics of Holstein Friesian. *Journal of Tekirdag Agricultural Faculty*, 10(3), 74–81. ISSN: 1302-7050
- Langbein, J., Siebert, K., & Nürnberg, G. (2009). On the use of an automated learning device by group-housed dwarf goats: Do goats seek cognitive challenges? *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 120(3), 150–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2009.07.006>
- Lee, J., Floyd, T., Erb, H., & Houpt, K. (2011). Preference and demand for exercise in stabled horses. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 130(3–4), 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2011.01.001>
- Leotti, L. A., & Delgado, M. R. (2011). The Inherent Reward of Choice. *Psychological Science*, 22, 1310–1318. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797611417005>
- Lesimple, C., Fureix, C., LeScolan, N., Richard-Yris, M.-A., & Hausberger, M. (2011). Housing conditions and breed are associated with emotionality and cognitive abilities in riding school horses. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 129(2–4), 92–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2010.11.005>
- Lesimple, C., Gautier, E., Benhajali, H., Rochais, C., Lunel, C., Bensaïd, S., Khalloufi, A., Henry, S., & Hausberger, M. (2019). Stall architecture influences horses' behaviour and the prevalence and type of stereotypies. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 219, 104833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2019.104833>
- Lesimple, C., Reverchon-Billot, L., Galloux, P., Stomp, M., Boichot, L., Coste, C., Henry, S., & Hausberger, M. (2020). Free movement: A key for welfare improvement in sport horses? *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 225, 104972. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2020.104972>

- Loberg, J., Telezhenko, E., Bergsten, C., & Lidfors, L. (2004). Behaviour and claw health in tied dairy cows with varying access to exercise in an outdoor paddock. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *89*(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2004.04.009>
- Luescher, U. A., McKEOWN, D. B., & Dean, H. (1998). A cross-sectional study on compulsive behaviour (stable vices) in horses. *Equine Veterinary Journal*, *30*(S27), 14–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2042-3306.1998.tb05138.x>
- Lürzel, S., Windschnurer, I., Futschik, A., & Waiblinger, S. (2016). Gentle interactions decrease the fear of humans in dairy heifers independently of early experience of stroking. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *178*, 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2016.02.012>
- Mandel, R., Whay, H. R., Klement, E., & Nicol, C. J. (2016). Invited review: Environmental enrichment of dairy cows and calves in indoor housing. *Journal of Dairy Science*, *99*(3), 1695–1715. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-9875>
- Mattiello, S. (2009). Welfare issues of modern deer farming. *Italian Journal of Animal Science*, *8*(sup1), 205–217. <https://doi.org/10.4081/ijas.2009.s1.205>
- Mason, G. J., Cooper, J., & Clarebrough, C. (2001). Frustrations of fur-farmed mink. *Nature*, *410*, 35–36. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35065157>
- McAfee, L. M., Mills, D. S., & Cooper, J. J. (2002). The use of mirrors for the control of stereotypic weaving behaviour in the stabled horse. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *78*(2–4), 159–173. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(02\)00086-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(02)00086-2)
- McDermott, J., & Hauser, M. D. (2007). Nonhuman primates prefer slow tempos but dislike music overall. *Cognition*, *104*(3), 654–668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2006.07.011>
- McDonnell, S. M. (1998). Reproductive behavior of donkeys (*Equus asinus*). *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *60*(2), 277–282. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(98\)00176-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(98)00176-2)
- Meagher, R. K., Weary, D. M., & von Keyserlingk, M. A. G. (2017). Some like it varied: Individual differences in preference for feed variety in dairy heifers. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *195*, 8–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2017.06.006>
- Mellor, D. J. (2016). Updating Animal Welfare Thinking: Moving beyond the ‘Five Freedoms’ towards ‘A Life Worth Living’. *Animals*, *6*(3), 21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani6030021>
- Mendl, M., & Paul, E. S. (2020). Animal affect and decision-making. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, *112*, 144–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2020.01.025>
- Mirabito, L., & Michel, V. (2003). L’aménagement des bâtiments de dindes: Une solution pour enrichir le milieu et réduire les lésions. *Sciences et Techniques Avicoles. Hors Série Bien-Être*, 22–27.
- Mysterud, A. (1998). Large male territories in a low-density population of roe deer *Capreolus capreolus* with small female home ranges. *Wildlife Biology*, *4*(4), 231–235. <https://doi.org/10.2981/wlb.1998.026>
- Nakayama, F., & Ninomiya, S. (2018). Evaluation of behavioural need of tethered cattle from jumping and running behaviour when they were released to the paddock. *Animal Behaviour and Management*, *54*(4), 165–172. https://doi.org/10.20652/abm.54.4_165
- Neave, H. W., Edwards, J. P., Thoday, H., Saunders, K., Zobel, G., & Webster, J. R. (2021). Do Walking Distance and Time Away from the Paddock Influence Daily Behaviour Patterns and Milk Yield of Grazing Dairy Cows? *Animals*, *11*(10), Article 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11102903>
- Newberry, R. C. (1995). Environmental enrichment: Increasing the biological relevance of captive environments. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, *44*(2–4), 229–243. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(95\)00616-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(95)00616-Z)
- Nicol, C. (2011). Chapter 2: Behaviour as an Indicator of Animal Welfare. In J. Webster (Ed.), *Management and Welfare of Farm Animals: The UFAW Farm Handbook* (5th edition), pp. 32–63. Wiley-Blackwell.

- Ninomiya, S., Kusunose, R., Sato, S., Terada, M., & Sugawara, K. (2004). Effects of feeding methods on eating frustration in stabled horses. *Animal Science Journal*, 75(5), 465–469. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1740-0929.2004.00214.x>
- Nowak, R., Kraïmi, N., Chaillou, E., Cornilleau, F., Devaux, M., Lévy, F., Parias, C., Boissy, A., Boivin, X., Mialon, M.-M., Bouvier, F., & Guilloteau, L. (2018). Artificial feeding in sheep and social enrichment: Potential beneficial effect of the presence of adult sheep on lambs health and welfare. *Rencontres Recherches Ruminants*, 24, 209-212. <http://www.journees3r.fr/spip.php?article4614>
- Oliveira, A. F. S., Rossi, A. O., Silva, L. F. R., Lau, M. C., & Barreto, R. E. (2010). Play behaviour in nonhuman animals and the animal welfare issue. *Journal of Ethology*, 28(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10164-009-0167-7>
- Pajor, E. A., Rushen, J., & de Passillé, A. M. B. (2000). Aversion learning techniques to evaluate dairy cattle handling practices. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 69(2), 89–102. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(00\)00119-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(00)00119-2)
- Perdue B. M., Evans T. A., Washburn D. A., Rumbaugh D. M., & Beran M. J. (2014) Do monkeys choose to choose? *Learning & Behavior*, 42, 164-175. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13420-014-0135-0>
- Pfaff, J., & Stecker, M. (1976). Loudness level and frequency content of noise in the animal house. *Laboratory Animals*, 10(2), 111–117. <https://doi.org/10.1258/002367776781071521>
- Piller, C. A. K., Stookey, J. M., & Watts, J. M. (1999). Effects of mirror-image exposure on heart rate and movement of isolated heifers. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 63(2), 93–102. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(99\)00010-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(99)00010-6)
- Popescu, S., Borda, C., Diugan, E. A., Spinu, M., Groza, I. S., & Sandru, C. D. (2013). Dairy cows welfare quality in tie-stall housing system with or without access to exercise. *Acta Veterinaria Scandinavica*, 55(1), 43. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1751-0147-55-43>
- Powell, D. (1995). Preliminary Evaluation of Environmental Enrichment Techniques for African Lions (*Panthera leo*). *Animal Welfare*, 4, 361–370.
- Price, E. O., & Thos, J. (1980). Behavioral responses to short-term social isolation in sheep and goats. *Applied Animal Ethology*, 6(4), 331–339. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3762\(80\)90133-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3762(80)90133-9)
- Proudfoot, K., & Habing, G. (2015). Social stress as a cause of diseases in farm animals: Current knowledge and future directions. *Veterinary Journal*, 206(1), 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tvjl.2015.05.024>
- Proudfoot, K. L., Weary, D. M., & von Keyserlingk, M. A. G. (2014). Maternal isolation behavior of Holstein dairy cows kept indoors1. *Journal of Animal Science*, 92(1), 277–281. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2013-6648>
- Provenza, F. D., Scott, C. B., Phy, T. S., & Lynch, J. J. (1996). Preference of sheep for foods varying in flavors and nutrients. *Journal of Animal Science*, 74(10), 2355–2361. <https://doi.org/10.2527/1996.74102355x>
- Rasmussen, E. B., Newland, M. C., & Hemmelman, E. (2020). The Relevance of Operant Behavior in Conceptualizing the Psychological Well-Being of Captive Animals. *Perspectives on Behavior Science*, 43(3), 617–654. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40614-020-00259-7>
- Raussi, S., Boissy, A., Andanson, S., Kaihilahti, J., Pradel, P., & Veissier, I. (2006). Repeated regrouping of pair-housed heifers around puberty affects their behavioural and HPA axis reactivities. *Animal Research*, 55(2), 131–144. <https://doi.org/10.1051/animres:2006004>
- Regula, G., Danuser, J., Spycher, B., & Wechsler, B. (2004). Health and welfare of dairy cows in different husbandry systems in Switzerland. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 66(1), 247–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2004.09.004>
- Rivera, E., Benjamin, S., Nielsen, B., Shelle, J., & Zanella, A. J. (2002). Behavioral and physiological responses of horses to initial training: The comparison between pastured versus stalled horses. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 78(2–4), 235–252. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(02\)00091-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(02)00091-6)

- Rochais, C., Henry, S., & Hausberger, M. (2018). "Hay-bags" and "Slow feeders": Testing their impact on horse behaviour and welfare. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 198, 52–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2017.09.019>
- Rørvang, M. V., & Nawroth, C. (2021). Advances in understanding cognition and learning in cattle. In M. Endres (Ed), *Understanding the behaviour and improving the welfare of dairy cattle*. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing.
- Rushen, J., Boissy, A., Terlouw, E. M., & de Passillé, A. M. (1999). Opioid peptides and behavioral and physiological responses of dairy cows to social isolation in unfamiliar surroundings. *Journal of Animal Science*, 77(11), 2918. <https://doi.org/10.2527/1999.77112918x>
- Rushen, J., & de Passillé, A. M. (1995). The motivation of non-nutritive sucking in calves, *Bos taurus*. *Animal Behaviour*, 49(6), 1503–1510. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-3472\(95\)90071-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-3472(95)90071-3)
- Seo, T., Sato, S., Kosaka, K., Sakamoto, N., Tokumoto, K., & Katoh, K. (1998). Development of tongue-playing in artificially reared calves: Effects of offering a dummy-teat, feeding of short cut hay and housing system. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 56(1), 1–12. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(97\)00078-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(97)00078-6)
- Shackleton, D., & Shank, C. (1984). A Review of the Social-Behavior of Feral and Wild Sheep and Goats. *Journal of Animal Science*, 58(2), 500–509. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas1984.582500x>
- Sharot T., De Martino B., & Dolan R. J. (2009). How Choice Reveals and Shapes Expected Hedonic Outcome. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 29, 3760–3765. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.4972-08.2009>
- Sluyter, F., & Van Oortmerssen, G. A. (2000). A Mouse is Not Just a Mouse. *Animal Welfare*, 9(2), 193–205.
- Søndergaard, E., Jensen, M. B., & Nicol, C. J. (2011). Motivation for social contact in horses measured by operant conditioning. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 132(3), 131–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2011.04.007>
- Spinka, M., & Wemelsfelder, F. (2018). Environmental Challenge and Animal Agency. In M. C. Appleby, I. A. S. Olsson & F. Galindo (Eds), *Animal welfare (3rd edition)*. CABI. 22. <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781786390202.0039>
- Stachurska, A., Pięta, M., Kloc, A., Bocian, K., & Cebera, M. (2013). Behavioural response to the toy in adult horses of various breeds, sexes and ages. *Annales Universitatis Mariae Curie-Skłodowska. Sectio EE Zootechnica*, 31(4), 61–67.
- Suzuki S. (1999) Selection of forced- and free-choice by monkeys (*Macaca fascicularis*). *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 88, 242–250. <https://doi.org/10.2466/PMS.88.1.242-250>
- Swaigood, R., & Shepherdson, D. (2008). Environmental enrichment as a strategy for mitigating stereotypies in zoo animals: A literature review and meta-analysis. In G. Mason & J. Rushen (Eds), *Stereotypic Animal Behaviour: Fundamentals and Applications to Welfare (2nd edition)*, 256. CABI Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1079/9780851990040.0256>
- Thorne, J. B., Goodwin, D., Kennedy, M. J., Davidson, H. P. B., & Harris, P. (2005). Foraging enrichment for individually housed horses: Practicality and effects on behaviour. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 94(1–2), 149–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2005.02.002>
- Tinker, M. K., White, N. A., Lessard, P., Thatcher, C. D., Pelzer, K. D., Davis, B., & Carmel, D. K. (1997). Prospective study of equine colic risk factors. *Equine Veterinary Journal*, 29(6), 454–458. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2042-3306.1997.tb03158.x>
- Trocino, A., Zomeno, C., Filiou, E., Birolo, M., White, P., & Xiccato, G. (2019). The Use of Environmental Enrichments Affects Performance and Behavior of Growing Rabbits Housed in Collective Pens. *Animals*, 9(8), 537. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani9080537>
- Tuytens, F. A. M. (2005). The importance of straw for pig and cattle welfare: A review. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 92(3), 261–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2005.05.007>

- Uetake, K., Hurnik, J. F., & Johnson, L. (1997). Effect of music on voluntary approach of dairy cows to an automatic milking system. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 53(3), 175–182. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(96\)01159-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(96)01159-8)
- Uexküll, J., & Kriszat, G. (2013). *Streifzüge durch die Umwelten von Tieren und Menschen Ein Bilderbuch unsichtbarer Welten: Einundzwanzigster Band*. Springer-Verlag.
- Van Diest, T. J., Kogan, C. J., & Kopper, J. J. (2021). The Effect of Water Flavor on Voluntary Water Intake in Hospitalized Horses. *Journal of Equine Veterinary Science*, 98, 103361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jevs.2020.103361>
- Vasantha, L., Jeyakumar, A., & Pitchai, M. A. (2003). Influence of music on the growth of koi carp, *Cyprinus carpio* (Pisces: *Cyprinidae*). *NAGA, WorldFish Center Quarterly*, 26(4), 25–26. <http://hdl.handle.net/1834/26169>
- Veissier, I., Andanson, S., Dubroeuq, H., & Pomiès, D. (2008). The motivation of cows to walk as thwarted by tethering1. *Journal of Animal Science*, 86(10), 2723–2729. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2008-1020>
- Veissier, I., Boissy, A., dePassillé, A. M., Rushen, J., van Reenen, C. G., Roussel, S., Andanson, S., & Pradel, P. (2001). Calves' responses to repeated social regrouping and relocation1. *Journal of Animal Science*, 79(10), 2580–2593. <https://doi.org/10.2527/2001.79102580x>
- Veissier, I., Boissy, A., Nowak, R., Orgeur, P., & Poindron, P. (1998). Ontogeny of social awareness in domestic herbivores. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 57(3), 233–245. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(98\)00099-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(98)00099-9)
- Visser, E. K., Ellis, A. D., & Van Reenen, C. G. (2008). The effect of two different housing conditions on the welfare of young horses stabled for the first time. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 114(3), 521–533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2008.03.003>
- Wang, M., & Schreiber, A. (2001). The impact of habitat fragmentation and social structure on the population genetics of roe deer (*Capreolus capreolus* L.) in Central Europe. *Heredity*, 86(6), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2540.2001.00889.x>
- Waring, G. H. (2003). *Horse Behavior* (2nd ed). Noyes Publishing. ISBN: 978-0-8155-1484-8
- Waters, A. J., Nicol, C. J., & French, N. P. (2002). Factors influencing the development of stereotypic and redirected behaviours in young horses: Findings of a four year prospective epidemiological study. *Equine Veterinary Journal*, 34(6), 572–579. <https://doi.org/10.2746/042516402776180241>
- Waynert, D. F., Stookey, J. M., Schwartzkopf-Genswein, K. S., Watts, J. M., & Waltz, C. S. (1999). The response of beef cattle to noise during handling. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 62(1), 27–42. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(98\)00211-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(98)00211-1)
- Weeks, C. A., & Nicol, C. J. (2006). Behavioural needs, priorities and preferences of laying hens. *Worlds Poultry Science Journal*, 62(2), 296–307. <https://doi.org/10.1079/WPS200598>
- Wells, D. L. (2009). Sensory stimulation as environmental enrichment for captive animals: A review. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 118(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2009.01.002>
- Wemelsfelder, F. (1993). The concept of animal boredom and its relationship to stereotyped behaviour. *Animal Welfare*, 35–47. ISBN: 0-85198-824-5
- Westerath, H. S., Gyax, L., & Hillmann, E. (2014). Are special feed and being brushed judged as positive by calves? *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 156, 12–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2014.04.003>
- Wilson, S. C., Mitlöhner, F. M., Morrow-Tesch, J., Dailey, J. W., & McGlone, J. J. (2002). An assessment of several potential enrichment devices for feedlot cattle. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 76(4), 259–265. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(02\)00019-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(02)00019-9)
- Würbel, H. (2009). Ethology applied to animal ethics. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 118(3), 118–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2009.02.019>

About EURCAW Ruminants & Equines

EURCAW Ruminants & Equines is the third European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare. It focuses on ruminant and equine welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle from birth to the end of life. EURCAW Ruminants & Equines' main objective is a harmonised compliance with EU legislation regarding welfare in EU Member States. This includes:

- Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept on farms;
- Regulations 1/2005/EC and 1099/2009/EC concerning their protection during transport and slaughter;
- Directive 2010/63/EU concerning the protection of animals used for scientific purposes;
- Directive 2008/119/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of calves.

EURCAW Ruminants & Equines supports:

- Inspectors of Competent Authorities (CAs);
- Ruminant and equine welfare policy workers;
- Bodies supporting CAs with scientific expertise, training, and communication.

Website and contact

EURCAW Ruminants & Equines' website offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of ruminant and equine welfare legislation.

We offer a 'Questions to EURCAW' service for official inspectors, policy workers, and other personnel providing advice or support for official controls of ruminant and equine welfare in the EU. For more information go to <https://www.eurcaw-ruminants-equines.eu/questions-to-eurcaw/>.

Activities of EURCAW Ruminants & Equines

- Coordinated Assistance
Providing support, networking and Questions to EURCAW;
- Welfare indicators, Assessment & Best Practice
Identifying animal welfare indicators, including animal based, management based and resource based indicators, that can be used to verify compliance with the EU legislation;
- Scientific and technical studies
Preparing Scientific Reviews of knowledge on welfare topics and identify research needs;
- Training
Developing training materials and training standards for official inspectors;
- Communication and Dissemination
Increasing awareness of our outputs via the website, twitter, and newsletter;

Partners

EURCAW Ruminants & Equines receives funding from DG SANTE of the European Commission and represents a collaboration between the following six partner institutions:

- Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden
- Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise "G. Caporale", Italy
- French National Institute for Agriculture, Food, and Environment, France
- University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria
- University College Dublin, Ireland
- Ellinikos Georgikos Organismos-Dimitra/Veterinary Research Institute, Greece